

Chlorophyll Content and Stress Tolerance Indices of Water Stressed *Corchorus Olitorus L.*

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Received: December 22, 2023; Accepted: May 4, 2023; Published: May 15, 2024

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11198281

Abstract: Water stress is an important parameter that affects plant growth. Little information is available on tolerance of *Corchorus olitorus* to moisture deficit and how this interferes with chlorophyll synthesis. This study investigated the impact of water stress on chlorophyll content and yield. A randomized complete block design was laid out, with irrigation schedule done at depths of 2, 4, 6 and 8 mm on a 2-day basis, replicated thrice. Data were collected on chlorophyll content using SPAD meter, yield (t/ha) and stress tolerance index. Chlorophyll content was highest on plot supplied irrigated water to a depth of 8 mm for both upper (78.7) and lower leaves (38.8). The yield at various water application depths were 0.7, 1.3, 2.6 and 3.5 t/ha for 2, 4, 6 and 8 mm depth of water application, respectively. The stress tolerance index was lowest (0.07) on plot supplied with water to a 2 mm depth, while highest (0.39) was on plot supplied with water to a depth of 8 mm. Optimum performance of the plant was observed at 8 mm depth of water application. Yield and chlorophyll content are directly related to level of water stress with stress tolerance index serving as a reliable stress investigative parameter.

Keywords: Water stress, Stress tolerance index, Chlorophyll content, yield, corchorus olitorus

Introduction

Plants are constantly exposed to water stress under agricultural conditions. The growth of plants and development are usually susceptible to water stress than other forms of biotic stresses (Zhu, 2002). Irrigation water

should be applied sufficiently and at the right time for proper water management and reduction of negative environmental effects (Calzadilla *et al.*, 2010). During plant growth moisture stress is an avoidable and crucial environmental variable that limits

photosynthesis (Dash and Mohanty, 2001; Malakouti *et al.*, 2005; Tanveer *et al.*, 2019). Adverse water stress impact include disruption of electron transport, decrease in water potential, increase in turgor pressure and reduction of photosynthetic pigments, which impairs plant growth, development and yield (Li *et al.*, 2019). Changes in growth response such as shrinking of tissues, changes in stomatal conductance due to changes in stomata pore sizes and accumulation of ion in tissues and low water potentials can be used to characterize adaptability of plants to water stress (Dash and Mohanty, 2001; Xu and Zhou, 2008). Stomatal regulation helps in deciding the rate of plant growth and development through photosynthesis. Photosynthesis is an important factor for various biochemical and physiological process to occur in plants (Verma *et al.*, 2020). The process occurs in chlorophyll, an organelle found in chloroplast of plants, algae and photoautotrophic bacteria. The chlorophyll is responsible for their green color that absorbs light for photosynthesis. Chlorophyll content reflects plant health condition and leaf photosynthesis abilities (Zulkarnaini *et al.*, 2019). Photosynthesis occurs in plant due to the presence of an important pigment called Chlorophyll. It serves as one of the major influence for crop yield and photosynthetic capacity. It is a key

parameter reflecting crop growth. Chlorophyll content estimations helps in assessing plant growth and water management which can influence crop yield and management decisions (Wu *et al.*, 2023). Changes in chlorophyll content in plants affects pigment concentration providing information on leaf development. The chlorophyll content declines as plants undergo stress (Yetik and Cndogan, 2022). The concentration of chlorophyll on the leaves can be used as a possible index in evaluating water stress impact on plants (Zobayed *et al.*, 2005). Chlorophyll content in plants and a higher carotenoid presence are associated with plant stress tolerance which in turn produces chlorophyll fluorescent. Adjustments of stomatal attributes, osmotic adjustment and antioxidant defense system activation are adaptation strategies initiated by plants to survive water stress impacts (Sharma *et al.*, 2020). Determination of concentration of chlorophyll in plant is an important parameter for studying the effect of various forms of stresses associated with leaf photosynthetic efficiency (Baker and Rosenqvist, 2004). Regulations of the stomata openings are prominent response plant exhibit against water stress (Song *et al.*, 2022). Besides, lower and upper leaf surfaces are stomata gateways for gas exchanges (Wankmüller and Carminati, 2022). In recent decades, changes

in climate, caused decrease in volume of rainfall distribution for both arid and semi-arid areas of the globe. As occurrences related to water stress impact becomes devastating, the need for adequate strategies in water management to reduce the difference between potential and actual yield of crops become very important (Ort, 2002). Chlorophyll concentration are influenced by factors which include: (i) intensity of light on the leaf chlorophyll (ii) temperature which plays a very critical role in chlorophyll efficiency and crop yield; and (iii) concentration of chlorophyll which is usually influenced by the age of leaf. During plant development phases, photosynthetic activity increases along leaf emergence phase and gradually decrease as the plant matures.

Plants becomes chlorotic when leaves turn old and yellow usually due to losses of chlorophyll (Ahmadi, 1985). Plant requires water in sufficient quantity to synthesize of chlorophyll. The concentration of chlorophyll increases after a heavy downpour, but the value decreases in dry season when it becomes marginal. Nevertheless, leaf chlorophyll content can also decline when the soil is saturated with water. The chlorophyll content in leaves of angiosperm under environmental stresses with susceptible cultivars decreases but increases its resistance. Leaf chlorosis also arises due to the influence

of environmental factors which accelerates loss of chlorophyll tissues under the influence of environmental stresses. (Khayatnezhad *et al.*, 2011).

Cultivars that are stress tolerant synthesize more chlorophyll compared to susceptible cultivars. The concentration of chlorophyll in cultivars that are stress tolerant increases as compared to non-stress tolerant cultivars. Generally, moisture stress causes reduction in chlorophyll concentration in crops but the extent to which a particular crop tolerates moisture deficit condition without affecting the crop negatively is crop dependent.

Corchorus olitorus is an important leaf vegetable cultivated for its mucilaginous foliage. The leaf is a rich source of many minerals, vitamins and antioxidants. Consumption of *C. olitorus* is important on wellness of gut system owing to its high concentration of dietary fibre. The leaves are rich in protein, iron, calcium, thiamine, niacin, riboflavin, folate and dietary fibre (Palada and Chang, 2003). Besides, Jute plants purifies the atmosphere by absorbing large quantity of CO₂, which unarguably can be regarded as one the major causes of the earth greenhouse effect. Jute plant theoretically, ingest CO₂ within the range of 15 tonnes from the air and releases close to 11 tonnes of oxygen in

hundred days of its growing season. Data has shown that CO₂ consumption rate by jute is greater than what is obtained for tree crops (Anwar, 2007). The importance of *C. olitorius* both as leaf vegetable and air cleaner are directly linked to its photosynthetic ability. However, information on chlorophyll concentration on *C. olitorius* leaf in response to moisture stress is scarcely known. This study aimed at understanding plant growth response to chlorophyll content changes due to variations in depth of water application. The need to understand the effect and concentration of chlorophyll in upper and lower leaves was very important. Therefore, the study investigated leaf chlorophyll content and yield relationships of *Corchorus olitorus* to water stress in Ibadan, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

The field study was carried out at the Department of Crop Protection and Environmental Biology's crop garden which is sited in the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. The study area is situated at 3°89' E and 7°45' N with elevation of 223.5±12.0 m above sea level. Irrigation was schedule on a 2-day basis at the depth of 2, 4, 6 and 8 mm on the experimental plot. The depth was determined based on volume/unit area. Drip irrigation method was adopted for supplying water at the pre-determined depth. A randomized complete block design method was adopted as

its treatment layout which was replicated thrice. Each vegetable bed size was 1 m x 1 m, however replicates were spaced 1m apart.

The viability of the seeds was first determined following standard procedures described by Islam *et al.* (2002). Seed dormancy was removed by priming method which was achieved by gentle pouring the jute seeds in a muslin cloth, wrap carefully then immerse in hot water (100°C) for about ten seconds, remove the cloth then allow to dry. *C. olitorus* propagation was carried out using broadcasting method. The seeds were sown at a seed rate of 3 g per m² then thinned to a spacing of 30 x 10 all in cm, giving 300,000 jute plants per hectare.

Leaf chlorophyll content was determined *in situ* with a portable handheld SPAD 502 Plus chlorophyll meter. Chlorophyll content at the upper leaves was measured by determining the content in the leaves located within 7 cm from the apex. Leaves located at the 7 cm down the ground were measured for determination of chlorophyll content at the lower leaves. The yield was determined by harvesting from the inner core area of 50 cm x 50 cm using a 50 cm² quadrat. The indicator used for the determination of the resistance and sensitivity of the crop under stressed condition was as described by (Fernandez,

1992). Stress tolerance index (STI) is indicator which can be determined with the expression: $STI = (Y_{Pi})(Y_{Si})/(Y_P)^2$

Where:

Y_{Pi} = yield of plant surface without stress

Y_{Si} = yield of stressed plant surface

Y_P = yield average of plant surface without stress.

Data Collection

Calibration of the SPAD meter was done with the aid of the manufactures reading checker. Concentration of chlorophyll at the top and bottom leaves were measured using a SPAD Meter in the field on a weekly basis. Leaf SPAD values recorded were obtained using the mean of 5 readings. Top leaves are regarded as leaves at the top parts, while bottom leaves are regarded as leaves at the lower parts of the plant. The yield of the crop was obtained by weighing the mass of freshly harvested leaves.

Statistical Analysis

Data collected on chlorophyll contents and plant yield were analyzed statistically. It was subjected to R 2.14.1 software (R Development Core Team, 2011) for Analysis

of Variance. Means were compared by adopting the LSD also known as least significant difference at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Chlorophyll content in the upper and lower leaves is shown in Figure 1. Concentration of chlorophyll was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in leaves from the upper part of the plant than the concentration in leaves from the lower part of the plant. The concentration of chlorophyll increase with increase in the depth of irrigation. Highest chlorophyll concentration (78.7 ± 6.7 SPAD unit) was recorded in leaves from upper parts of *C. olitorius* irrigated at 8 mm depth. However, concentration of chlorophyll was lowest (33.3 ± 1.2 SPAD unit) in leaf from the lower part (Figure 1).

Water stress affected the yield of *C. olitorius* significantly as indicated in Figure 2. Yield was significantly higher (3.5 g) in plant irrigated at 8 mm depth relative to other treatments. The yield was significantly lower (0.7 g) in plant irrigated at 2 mm depth than the other treatments. Optimum performance of the plant was observed at 8 mm depth of water application.

Figure 1 Chlorophyll Content (SPAD value) at different irrigation regimes

Figure 2 Yield of *C. olitorius* in response to different irrigation regimes

The yield of *C. olitorius* was related directly with the concentration of chlorophyll in leaves of the crop located at the different parts of the plant. The result showed that influence of drought on yield of *C. olitorius* was directly related ($r=0.9728$) to the

concentration of chlorophyll in lower leaves (Figure 3a). Similarly, yield of *C. olitorius* is explained by 92% of concentration of chlorophyll in the upper leaves. The concentration of chlorophyll in the upper leaves is directly related ($r=0.9805$) to yield

of the crop in response to drought (Figure 3b). Highest yield value of 3.5 t/ha was observed at a lower chlorophyll concentration of 38.8 in the lower leaves. However, in the upper leaves higher concentration of chlorophyll (78.7) is required to produce 3.5 t/ha leaf yield under drought condition.

Highest chlorophyll concentration was recorded in plant irrigated at 8 mm depth but

this was not significantly higher than the chlorophyll content recorded in plant irrigated at 2 and 6 mm depth. Lowest concentration of chlorophyll was recorded in plant irrigated at 4 mm depth (Figure 4b). The yield of *C. olitorius* is directly related to the irrigation depth. The yield was lower at shallow irrigation depth (2 mm) compared to yield obtained when irrigation was deeper (8 mm).

Figure 3 Relationship between leaf yield and chlorophyll content at lower (a) and upper (b) leaves

Figure 4 Average chlorophyll content at different irrigation regimes (a) and relationship between yield and irrigation depth (b).

Chlorophyll content was significantly higher in upper leaves than in the lower leaves of water stressed *C. olitorius* (Figure 5). The chlorophyll content of leaves above was relatively high at different irrigation regimes as shown in Figure 6. The values obtained ranged from 0.073 at 2 mm irrigation depth to

0.388 at 8 mm irrigation regime. The STI value of 0.388 was significantly higher at 8 mm irrigation depth, while the STI value of 0.073 was obtained at irrigation depth of 2 mm. This readily shows that as the depth of water application increases the STI value increases.

Figure 5 Average chlorophyll content in above and below leaves

Figure 6 Chlorophyll content of above leaf at different irrigation regimes

The highest chlorophyll content recorded in the upper part of plant indicated that high photosynthetic activity occurred at the upper part of plant than the lower parts of the plants. This is possibly because leaves at the upper parts are well exposed to solar radiation than the leaves at the lower parts. The direct contact with sunlight accelerates the rate of photosynthesis production in response to incidence or intensity of sun rays.

Growth of leaf vegetables such as *Corchorus olitorius* depends on availability of water for photosynthesis. In addition, moisture availability is necessary for modifying temperature, gaseous exchange in leaf vegetables. Hence most leaf vegetables especially *C. olitorius* are not drought tolerant. This is because chlorophyll, a major component required for photosynthesis needs water to function. Khayatnezhad *et al.* (2011), stated that water stress resistant plants, increases their chlorophyll content in leaves to adapt to inclement environmental conditions. This assertion does not apply to the result obtained in this experiment. This perhaps suggest that *C. olitorius* is not tolerant of water stress condition. The chlorophyll present in the leaves crucially aid the process of photosynthesis which is a phenomenon for manufacturing of food by plants. The chlorophyll content in top leaves were higher

than those of the lower leaves. This shows that the process of photosynthesis in the crop occurs more on the upper leaves than the lower leaves. It can be deduced that the upper leaves of plants are very important in plant growth and development than leaves at the lower parts since they receive solar inception directly before the leaves located at the lower parts. Sunlight, usually intercepted more by the upper leaves play significant role in chlorophyll synthesis under sufficient moisture condition. It is suffice to imply that leaves at the upper part of plant are pivotal to chlorophyll synthesis and ultimately photosynthesis. To ensure adequate growth and development of *C. olitorius*, moisture must be optimal for sufficient chlorophyll synthesis especially at upper leaves. It is therefore imperative to prevent moisture stress to reduce natural leaf abscission resulting from moisture deficit.

Changes in water stress patterns affect plant growth and development, yield and soil stability. Water deficit stress affects physiological and morphological aspects of the plant; the level, extent and type of damage is influenced by the plant resistance and stress intensity. This implies that a higher STI value is a desirable trait and pivotal to minimizing moisture stress in leaf vegetable of high economic value.

The relationship among Stress Tolerance Index, osmotic stress and leaf yield in *C. olitorius* was well elucidated in this study. Water application regimes with higher STI value resulted in higher leaf yield. This also proved that plants experiencing minimal water stress threshold would still produce better yield compared to situations where plants suffer severe moisture deficit. The STI can therefore be relied upon as it was able to identify the crop suffering from excruciating moisture stress.

Moisture stress is known to facilitate stomatal closure causing photorespiration thereby damaging the chloroplast. This could be the reason why under inadequate irrigation, low chlorophyll concentration was recorded. Since there was low chlorophyll content at the suboptimal irrigation, it therefore means that photosynthesis will be minimal which probably caused the low fresh leaf yield recorded. Our view is similar to findings from Khayatnzhad *et al.* (2011), who noticed reduction in yield as water deficit upsurges. The study disclosed that an increase in the amount of water supplied is vital for the growth and development of *C. olitorius*. However, soil water reduction will significantly affect crop performance (Khan *et al.*, 2021). Optimal performance of the plant was observed at 6 mm depth of water

application. Whereas, suboptimal water availability would inhibit crop development and modulate guard cell movement which is responsible for stomata functioning. Whatever interferes with optimal functioning of stomata will have direct effect of photosynthesis (Wankmüller and Carminati, 2022).

Conclusion

There was a significant relationship between chlorophyll content and fresh yield of *Corchorus olitorius*. The chlorophyll content in leaves of upper parts of the plants plays a better role in photosynthesis than leaves at the lower part of the plant. Stress tolerance index is a reliable parameter that can easily depict the impact of water stress on the plant without necessary taking into consideration other water stress parameters. The estimated chlorophyll content using the SPAD meter reveals that chlorophyll content of leaves in the top most part was higher compared to those at the lower parts. In future studies on water stress, the use of stress tolerance index as a quick and reliable parameter should be encouraged.

Author Contributions

Ehumadu C. N.: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources and manuscript writing; **Ewemoje T. A.:** Project

administration, Supervision, Validation and manuscript writing while **Dada O. A.:** Methodology, Supervision, Validation, and manuscript writing. All authors read and approved the manuscript..

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to appreciate the following Departments; Crop Protection and Environmental Biology, Agricultural and Environmental Engineering, and Agronomy, situated in the prestigious University of Ibadan, Nigeria, for providing land, equipment and constructive comments for the actualization of this study.

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